

A newbie question is just an inappropriately structured question

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Abstract:	ChatGPT and other chatbots are tools for quickly and often without humiliation, getting a summary answer to a question. This distinguishes questions directed to artificial intelligence from questions directed to people, who in discussion and questioning communities, sometimes humiliate newcomers instead of realizing that someone new to a particular field will logically not use terms and process descriptions common in that field. That is what this essay is about because novice questions can often be slightly modified and become not personal questions but general questions, while elsewhere, it is enough to request details in the form of a broader description, photos, or videos.
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Questions as a supplementary study tool

Asking questions about how something works and how to do something is an essential human trait. People often learn new things this way because they can do something, for example, by imitating someone else. Copying is thus, in its most original sense, one of the most important ways of learning. With the advent of printing, asking questions was transferred to book owners, libraries, and, more recently, to the Internet. The original essence of search engines was to search for information. With the development of the web, specialized websites focused on answering questions have also appeared. Students learning something and coming across things they need help understanding often ask questions. For them, it is a supplementary study tool, where the primary study medium is usually the course they attend.

Newbie questions are incomprehensible

Most questions are usually asked by those new to a field, and some newsgroups limit the number of questions newcomers can ask in a given time. For older community members, beginner questions are annoying, and perhaps the goal of the restriction is to encourage the newcomers to work independently, that is, to find answers to some questions themselves and not rely on someone to answer all their questions. This measure needs to be set up appropriately so that it does not discourage newcomers but, at the same time, does not flood the site with beginner questions. If it is a helpful community¹, this community must understand that beginners are full of energy, they do not understand many things, and so they will have many questions, and that new newcomers appear more and more, so these questions will continue to circulate.

In addition to the fact that newcomers often have many questions in a short period, and these questions may seem to lay to someone - and I write seem because some newcomers are wise and, on the contrary, have advanced and philosophical questions which is not expected - newcomers may have problems with the correct structure of questions because they do not understand the given issue, do not understand the processes and do not know the terminology, or have problems in general with the structure of the language.

Contempt for newbie questions and a simple fix

Poorly structured questions, with poorly used terminology and poorly described processes, are contemptuously tagged as private questions, private problems, etc., and eventually deleted. Minor adjustments often are enough to turn a so-called "me" question into a general, quickly answered one. Some older members seem to discard these questions the moment the pronoun "me" appears in the question. However, if we depersonalize the question, it becomes an entirely valid question for such a person.

¹ A paradox in this area is the Stack Overflow website, which still presents as a helpful community built on questions. It certainly played this role shortly after its inception, but now, after several years of existence, it resembles more of a knowledge base because beginner questions are rarely accepted. The discrepancy between the functioning and communication of the project can then be another problem of question-based communities.

ChatGPT as a tireless debater with newbies

One solution to this problem is to be aware of it at all. A discussion platform can create a template for newbie questions and help them ask the question in a way that is understandable to professionals, for example, by finding out more information from the newbie. In addition to simply asking a question, it can request additional detailed information, photos, or videos from the newbie and, based on that, guess what the person is asking and help them with terminology. At the same time, the newbie can be motivated after getting an understanding of a topic; they will only be able to enter questions and will not have to explain everything in detail.

Lay questions could be removed after they have been answered. However, this does not solve human fatigue and the problem of some Internet communities needing equally strong generations. AI-based chat systems may take over this role in the future. For example, in version 4 of chatGPT, the bot seems to be able to understand a poorly structured question for a given field, and if it does not understand it right away, a few more clarifying information help it. Over time, chatbots may completely replace question communities, as they will answer questions quickly, tirelessly, and most importantly, without the contempt and insults that older community members sometimes inflict on newcomers.